

ISic0691

I.Sicily inscription 0691

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR081493

0. [---]

1. [---] A (uli) f (ilio) Qu [ir (ina) ---]

2. [--- Euc]arpia ux [or ---].

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175750

EDR 081493

EDCS 6100259

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0338k

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 165 no.19 fig.19

Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 83 no.30 fig.56

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